

MAGNETIC STUDY OF SOME METAL DERIVATIVES OF
1 : 3- β -DIKETONES. PART I

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The diamagnetic susceptibilities of eleven metal acetylacetonates, namely, that of Be, Mg, Zn, Cd, Hg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Al, Zr and Th, have been studied. The results show the absence of singlet linkages in these compounds and appear to support the structure involving single and double bonds. The fair agreement between the observed and the calculated values of molar susceptibilities for all metal chelates except those of Zn, Cd and Hg suggests that there is no systematic and appreciable diamagnetic contribution due to the metal chelate bond in these compounds.

A study of the measurements of infra-red spectra (Duval, Freymann and Le Compte, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1952, 106) and of the vibration spectra (Duval *et al.*, *Compt. rend.*, 1950, 231, 272 ; Skoldinov and Shegorin, *Zur. Phiz. Chim.*, 1950, 24, 955) of several metal derivatives of acetylacetonone has led to the conclusion that these metal derivatives of acetylacetonone exist only in the enolic form and that they are complexes, rather than salts. The metal derivatives of acetylacetonone are therefore looked upon as chelate compounds. It appears from the literature that so far no systematic work has been done on the magnetic measurements of these metal chelates of acetylacetonone.

Angus and Farquharson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, 136A, 579) studied the diamagnetic susceptibility of the beryllium acetylacetonone. The susceptibility of thorium acetylacetonone was determined by Hutchisson and Elliott (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 16, 920) with a view to ascertaining whether the chelated group had any diamagnetic correction to be applied in such compounds. In the present communication the diamagnetic susceptibility of several metal chelates of acetylacetonone has been determined and the results discussed from the viewpoint of the structure of metal chelates. The diamagnetic contribution of the chelate group attached to the metal atom has also been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

The metal chelates of acetylacetonone, namely, Be, Mg, Zn, Cd, Hg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Al, Th and Zr acetylacetonates, were prepared by the known methods, using acetylacetonone of Merck's quality and the inorganic salts of very high purity. Acetylacetonone was twice distilled in a glass-joint apparatus before use. The compounds so prepared were carefully purified by repeated crystallisation and dried before measurement. The purity of the compounds was determined by m.p. and analysis of the metal content.

Diamagnetic Susceptibility Measurements.—The diamagnetic susceptibilities of these compounds were determined by a modified form of Gouy's balance (*Compt. rend.*, 1889, 109, 935). Angus and Tilston (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 43, 235) have recently obtained the usual equation for calculating the diamagnetic susceptibility in the following form :

$$\chi = \frac{\alpha F + C}{w} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

could only be represented by a structure involving singlet linkages. The existence of singlet linkages in normal and stable compounds is, however, highly improbable on quantum mechanical consideration, because a stable one-electron bond can be formed only when there are two conceivable electronic states of the system with essentially the same energy. The structure involving singlet linkages is therefore obviously ruled out.

The magnetic data obtained for these metal chelates (Table I) also indicate the absence of singlet linkages, as all the compounds are diamagnetic. If these metal chelates had single electron bonds, they would have shown an overwhelming paramagnetism due to unpaired electrons.

Calculation of χ of Acetylacetonate Ion.—The susceptibility of acetylacetonate ion has been calculated on the basis of the structure represented as above, by using Pascal's constants (Bhatnagar and Mathur, "Physical Principles and Application of Magneto-Chemistry", p. 94) for various atoms and constitutive correction factors. Accordingly, the structure of this ion is represented as

so that its susceptibility is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= [5\text{C}] + [7\text{H}] + [-\text{O}-] + [= \text{O}] + \Sigma\lambda \\ &= -30.0 - 20.51 - 4.61 + 1.73 + \Sigma\lambda \\ &= -53.29 + \Sigma\lambda \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where } \Sigma\lambda &= 2\text{C}_s^a + \text{C}_s^b + [\text{C}=\text{C}] \\ &= -2.58 - 0.48 + 5.50 \\ &= +2.44 \\ &= -50.95 \times 10^{-6} \end{aligned}$$

Comparison of Molar Susceptibilities.—The observed molar susceptibilities of the metal chelates were compared with the values calculated by using the value of the acetylacetonate ion as computed above and the Angus values (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, 136A, 569) for various metal atoms. The observed and calculated values of molar susceptibilities χ_M are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Acetyl acetate.	χ_M		Acetyl acetate.	χ_M		Acetyl acetate.	χ_M	
	Obs.	Calc.		Obs.	Calc.		Obs.	Calc.
Be	107.50	102.25	Hg	117.20	149.47	Ba	130.90	133.49
Mg	106.30	104.79	Ca	113.20	112.32	Al	151.10	155.13
Zn	121.60	130.32	Sr	127.70	122.09	Zr	212.00	218.59
Cd	121.40	135.84				Th	233.70	229.70

Table II shows that for all the metal chelates, except those of Zn, Cd and Hg, the observed values of χ_M agree fairly well with the calculated ones; slight differences are, of course, expected since the theoretical values used are for free ions. The fair agreement between the observed and calculated values of χ_M indicates that there is no systematic and appreciable diamagnetic contribution due to the metal chelate bond in these compounds. However, the differences observed in the case of Zn, Cd and Hg acetylacetonates are significant, and they are in the order of $8.72 < 14.44 < 32.77$. These results therefore suggest that at least in these metal chelates, there is an appreciable depression in diamagnetism due to the metal chelate bond which increases in the order: $Zn < Cd < Hg$.

It may be concluded therefore that for all metal chelates, except of Zn, Cd and Hg, there is no appreciable diamagnetic contribution due to the metal chelate bond. This is in agreement with the conclusion deduced by Hutchisson and Elliott from a study of thorium acetylacetonate.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. C. R. Kanekar for helpful suggestions and interest in this investigation. Thanks are due to Dr. L. N. Mulay who initiated this work.

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Received October 1, 1956.